

GEOPHYSICAL MONITORING FOR SUSTAINABLE MINING: CASE STUDIES USING ELECTRICAL RESISTIVITY TOMOGRAPHY

Bogdana Milenkovich

University of Mining and Geology “St. Ivan Rilski”, 1700 Sofia; E-mail: b.milenkovic@mgu.bg

ABSTRACT. The application of geophysical methods at all stages of mining operations and facility management significantly enhances the understanding of the dynamics of geotechnical and hydrogeological processes. The use of electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) as part of an integrated system for sustainable mine planning supports the achievement of higher standards of safety and sustainability. The development of standardised protocols for geophysical monitoring, as well as the implementation of automated and long-term observation systems, would contribute to the timely diagnosis of potential risks and improved security of mining sites. The systematic application of this method, in combination with drilling data and engineering and geological information, provides a reliable basis for informed decision-making in favour of environmental protection, facility safety, and public trust.

Key words: mines, monitoring, geophysics, electrical resistivity tomography (ERT).

ГЕОФИЗИЧЕН МОНИТОРИНГ ЗА УСТОЙЧИВО РАЗВИТИЕ НА МИННАТА ДЕЙНОСТ: ПРИМЕРИ С ИЗПОЛЗВАНЕ НА ЕЛЕКТРОТОМОГРАФИЯ

Богдана Миленкович

Минно-геоложки университет „Св. Иван Рилски“, 1700 София

РЕЗЮМЕ. Прилагането на геофизични методи във всички етапи от експлоатацията и управлението на минните обекти и съоръжения значително подобрява разбирането за динамиката на геотехническите и хидрогеоложки процеси. Използването на електротомография (ERT) като част от интегрираната система за устойчиво планиране в мините подпомага постигането на по-високи стандарти за безопасност и устойчивост. Разработването на стандартизирани протоколи за геофизичен мониторинг, както и въвеждането на автоматизирани и дългосрочни системи за наблюдение, биха допринесли за навременна диагностика на потенциални рискове и повишена сигурност на минните обекти. Систематичното приложение на този метод в комбинация със сондажи и инженерно-геоложки данни осигурява надеждна основа за вземане на информирани решения в полза на околната среда, безопасността на съоръженията и общественото доверие.

Ключови думи: минни обекти, мониторинг, геофизика, електротомография.

Introduction

The sustainable management of mining operations has become an increasingly important concern in the context of environmental responsibility, public safety, and long-term economic efficiency. As mining activities inevitably alter the geological and hydrological regimes of the subsurface environment, a comprehensive understanding of geotechnical and hydrogeological processes is essential throughout the entire lifecycle of a mining project — from exploration and extraction to waste management and site closure (Hristov and Aleksandrova, 2000). As Yankova (2021) mentions, some of the largest damages and environment contamination is caused by mining. In this context, geophysical methods have emerged as invaluable tools for non-invasive and cost-effective subsurface investigation.

According to many authors, among these methods, electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) has gained widespread attention due to its high sensitivity to variations in lithology, porosity, saturation, and fluid conductivity. The application of ERT in mining environments enables the detection and spatial characterisation of critical subsurface features, such as saturated zones, structural discontinuities, and material compaction. Its integration into monitoring programs supports proactive risk management and enhances the ability to detect early signs of instability or environmental hazards (Dimovski et al., 2020; Tomova, 2023; Tomova & Kisyov, 2023).

The adoption of ERT as part of a broader, integrated system for sustainable mine planning contributes to the realisation of higher safety and environmental standards. When applied systematically during key operational stages — such as tailings

dam construction, drainage evaluation, post-closure stability assessment or detection of geological hazards, such as voids, cavities, and abandoned workings within the mine — ERT provides continuous insights into the evolving conditions of the subsurface (Tomova, 2024). This approach allows for the implementation of real-time decision-making process and helps identify potential geotechnical risks before they develop into failures.

Furthermore, the development of standardised geophysical monitoring protocols, combined with the implementation of automated, long-term observation networks, offers a forward-looking solution for mining companies seeking to align with international best practices in environmental and social governance. Furthermore, geophysical surveys for identifying hard inclusions in the open-pit horizons of the East Maritsa Basin can be cited as good mining practices (Zlatanov and Aleksandrova, 2008). When coupled with drilling data and engineering-geological models, geophysical methods provide a reliable, multidimensional framework for decision-making, supporting not only operational safety but also building public trust and ensuring regulatory compliance.

Methodology

This paper presents the application and interpretation of ERT data in a mining context, with a focus on its use for monitoring the hydrodynamic behaviour of tailings storage facilities and understanding the subsurface conditions and optimising mining operations. The study illustrates how geophysical techniques, particularly ERT, can be effectively

integrated into routine mine monitoring workflows to improve the overall resilience and sustainability of mining infrastructure.

As Bharti (Bharti et al., 2023) stated, ERT is a versatile tool for the mapping of subsurface features like voids, cavities, underground galleries/tunnels (air-or water-filled), and so on, where high contrast in resistivity is leveraged to delineate the features very easily.

Many authors have stated that the purpose of electrical surveys is to determine the subsurface resistivity distribution by making measurements on the ground surface. The ERT method is appropriate for two-dimensional mapping of the near-surface area in vertical sections along the surveyed lines (Loke, 1999; Dimovski & Stoyanov, 2020). Aleksandrova (2008) points out that when combined with hydrogeological data, ERT can provide essential information for the design and stability assessment of waste storage facilities.

Electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) is a non-invasive geophysical technique that images the subsurface by measuring the spatial distribution of electrical resistivity. The method is based on injecting a known electrical current into the ground using a pair of electrodes and recording the resulting voltage difference at other electrode pairs. These measurements are used to compute the apparent resistivity of the subsurface, which is then inverted to generate a 2D or 3D model representing the true resistivity distribution.

ERT is particularly effective in environments where contrasts in resistivity correspond to variations in lithology, porosity, fracture density, or moisture content. Because water-saturated zones typically exhibit lower resistivity compared to dry or compacted materials, ERT is widely used for detecting groundwater, monitoring seepage, and delineating weak or fractured zones — all of which are critical in both underground mine tunnels and tailings storage facilities.

The method's sensitivity to changes in subsurface conditions makes it especially suitable for dynamic monitoring applications. In mining contexts, ERT enables early detection of geotechnical instabilities, fracture zones, and zones of anomalous saturation, which may pose risks to infrastructure integrity. The technique is also effective in evaluating the performance of drainage systems and identifying potential pathways for contaminant migration.

Field data are acquired using electrode arrays (e.g., Wenner, Dipole–Dipole, or Schlumberger), with the choice of configuration depending on the required resolution and depth of investigation. Modern ERT systems typically include an automated switching unit that allows sequential activation of numerous electrodes (often 48 to 96 or more), significantly improving acquisition speed and data density. The apparent resistivity values collected in the field are processed using inversion software, such as RES2DINV (Loke, 2001), which iteratively adjusts a subsurface model to minimise the misfit between observed and calculated values (de Groot-Hedlin and Constable, 1990; Loke and Barker, 1996).

The final output consists of resistivity cross-sections that can be interpreted in terms of geological structure, fluid saturation, and mechanical properties. When combined with geological, hydrogeological, and geotechnical data, ERT provides a reliable foundation for risk assessment and decision-making in complex mining environments.

However, 2-D electrical surveys are now practical commercial techniques with the relatively recent development of multi-electrode resistivity surveying instruments (Griffiths et al., 1990) and fast computer inversion software (Loke, 1994).

Case study: Stability assessment in underground mining conditions

In the present study, stability assessment was carried out for a part of an underground mine tunnel. As Tomova and Kisyov (2024a) pointed out, a lot of case studies worldwide demonstrate the efficacy of geophysical methods in detecting underground uncertainties. The detection and characterisation of subsurface uncertainties, such as fractures, faults, cavities, zones of high porosity, or variable saturation, remain central challenges in geotechnical engineering, hydrogeology, and mining operations. Geophysical methods, especially non-invasive techniques, such as electrical resistivity tomography (ERT), offer cost-effective, spatially continuous, and high-resolution imaging capabilities that complement direct investigation methods like drilling and sampling (Reynolds, 2011).

Among these techniques, ERT has proven particularly effective for mapping electrical resistivity variations related to lithological heterogeneities, water content, fault zones, and voids. The method is especially valuable in environments where direct access is limited or where continuous monitoring is required to assess temporal variations, such as in tunnels, mine waste storage facilities, and unstable slopes.

Resistivity surveys give a picture of the subsurface resistivity distribution. To convert the resistivity picture into a geological picture, some knowledge of typical resistivity values for different types of subsurface materials and the geology of the area surveyed is important.

ERT effectively images structural features, such as faults, fractures, and cavities, even when they are not visually observable, enabling early detection of geotechnical hazards in mining settings.

To demonstrate the ability of ERT to face this challenge, a line measured on the ceiling of a mine gallery is shown (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Part of a mine gallery, where an ERT line is recorded

The measured ERT line is shown in Figure 2.

The interpretation of the zones marking the spatial distribution of an environment with reduced electrical resistivity values - in the range from 0.1 to about 1 Ωm - probably marks the presence of mylonitised, clayey areas, very likely hydrated, also part of the active fault system.

Fig. 2. The ERT line measured on the ceiling of a mine gallery

The contact marking the two environments can trace the boundaries of the spatial distribution of each of the zones thus separated, even though the contact difference in their electrical resistance is not noticeably sharp.

Fracture zones, which typically manifest as localised zones of low resistivity due to increased porosity and water content, can be accurately delineated through dense electrode arrays and high-resolution inversion models.

When used alongside borehole data, ERT provides reliable and spatially continuous subsurface information, enhancing the detection and characterisation of underground weaknesses before failure occurs.

The interpretation made confirms the activity and complex nature of the fault system, which is important in planning future mining activities and assessing geotechnical risk.

The identified heterogeneities in the rock massif, especially the areas with reduced electrical resistivity values, should be subject to additional control and monitoring, given their possible connection with waterlogged areas.

The geophysical surveys conducted demonstrate the significant potential of geophysical methods, and in particular electrical tomography, as an effective tool for geotechnical assessment. Although these methods are traditionally associated with the search and exploration of mineral resources, their application in engineering-geological and geotechnical tasks is becoming increasingly significant, especially in the context of assessing the quality of the rock mass, determining geological structures, and hydrogeological conditions in the design and development of mines.

In conclusion, the applied methodology shows high efficiency in clarifying the geological situation and can be successfully used as part of the preliminary studies for mining design purposes.

Case study: Stability assessment in an Integrated Mine Waste Storage Facility

In an extensive review, Tomova and Kisyov (2024b) report that Integrated Mine Waste Storage Facilities (IMWF) often consist of various components, such as tailings dams, waste rock dumps, and water management structures. Monitoring techniques like geophysical methods can provide valuable information on factors, such as slope movements, deformation behavior, and physical properties of the materials in the facility. This knowledge is essential for conducting risk assessments, helps in identifying potential hazards, and in evaluating the associated risks. Implementing reliable monitoring systems is crucial for early detection of potential stability issues.

The concept of the Integrated Mine Waste Storage Facility (IMWSF) involves the accumulation of a thickened tailings layer within cells constructed from waste rock and soil. The competent waste rock provides the structural strength necessary for the

overall stability of the facility and also functions as a drainage medium for fluids within the cells.

The construction of such an integrated facility directly links mining operations with tailings deposition, as the formation and stability of the cells require the availability of competent waste rock (Eldridge et al., 2011).

The Integrated Mine Waste Storage Facility (IMWSF) is designed to function as a fully self-draining structure. A drainage system has been constructed at the base of each cell within the facility, which channels water into one of two reservoirs located at the end of the facility. To minimise the formation of ponded water, the facility is engineered with a "honeycomb" structure, which reduces the length of drainage paths (both horizontally and vertically) and optimises the system's capacity to discharge water (Diaz, 2014).

Tailings consolidation plays a vital role in ensuring the overall stability of these facilities. Since tailings are typically composed of finely ground rock particles, water, and residual processing reagents, their unconsolidated state can pose serious geotechnical and environmental risks. The effective consolidation of tailings, often aided by chemical or mechanical treatment, contributes to increased material strength and reduced pore water pressures, thereby improving the integrity of the storage structure (Dimitrov & Grigorova, 2023).

For this purpose, geophysical surveys based on electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) are implemented in IMWFs. ERT's sensitivity to changes in saturation, porosity, and mineral composition enables the detection of geotechnical anomalies that may not be readily apparent through traditional monitoring approaches (Hasan et al., 2021). This makes ERT a powerful tool for assessing consolidation processes and identifying zones where drainage or material behaviour may compromise structural stability.

The measurement is performed along a profile with a length of 760 meters. The measurements were conducted using a four-electrode Wenner-Schlumberger array configuration. Data acquisition was performed with the Australian-made ZZ Universal 96-Channel Resistivity/IP Meter (Figure 3). This equipment allows for the measurement of the specific electrical resistivity of the subsurface and can also be effectively used for registering both self-potential and induced polarisation signals.

Fig. 3. The ZZ Universal 96-Channel Resistivity/IP Meter on the terrain

The ZZ Universal 96 system is equipped with the FlashRES-UNIVERSAL 96 technology, which enables the simultaneous utilisation of all electrodes, thus collecting a higher volume of data along the profile. This capability allows for greater flexibility in electrode layout and significantly enhances the accuracy and reliability of the electrical resistivity tomography results. The FlashRES-UNIVERSAL 96 system includes 93 channels and can simultaneously collect data from 93 points during each current injection cycle along the survey line.

The registered ERT line measured in the Integrated Mine Waste Storage Facility (IMWSF) is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. ERT line measured in the Integrated Mine Waste Storage Facility

To perform a deeper measurement, a cable with a distance between the electrodes of 10 meters was used when recording the electrical resistivity profile along the line. In this way, the resulting image reaches a depth of 160 meters and confidently highlights the natural terrain and the size of the cells. The distribution of the deposited material, limited by the natural terrain, the road between the two valleys and the surface, is also clearly visible.

Zones exhibiting low electrical resistivity along the measured profiles are most likely indicative of water-saturated regions, attributed to incomplete drainage within the cell structure. The extent and geometry of these low-resistivity anomalies observed along the line are plausibly influenced by the overburden pressure exerted by the superimposed mine waste, as well as the varying degrees of material consolidation over time.

Furthermore, temporal variability in the spatial distribution and intensity of these low-resistivity zones may be associated with seasonal environmental factors such as precipitation, temperature fluctuations, and so on. These external conditions can affect moisture content and pore water distribution, thereby modulating the electrical properties of the subsurface materials.

Conclusions

The application of electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) in mining-related geotechnical investigations demonstrates significant potential for improving environmental safety and operational sustainability. In the first case study, the deployment of ERT within an underground mine tunnel effectively delineated low-resistivity zones, interpreted as potential fault or fracture zones. This geophysical insight supports risk reduction strategies for underground infrastructure and enhances geological understanding, particularly in areas inaccessible by direct observation.

In the second case study, ERT was implemented as part of an integrated geophysical monitoring program within an Integrated Mine Waste Storage Facility (IMWSF). The results revealed areas with anomalously low resistivity values, indicating zones of elevated saturation or incomplete

consolidation. These findings correspond with seasonal and operational variables, such as precipitation, drainage efficiency, and deposition loading. The integration of ERT data with hydrogeological and geotechnical information allowed for a more comprehensive understanding of fluid migration, cell drainage behavior, and material consolidation within the facility.

The systematic use of ERT across various phases of mining operations – from underground exploration to surface waste management – enables non-invasive, real-time assessment of critical subsurface conditions. This approach strengthens early warning capabilities, supports informed decision-making, and aligns with best practices for sustainable and safe mining. Furthermore, the adoption of standardised protocols and automated monitoring systems, as highlighted in the reviewed literature, enhances the long-term reliability of such geophysical surveillance, reinforcing the role of ERT as a core component of modern mine monitoring systems.

The results of the electrical sections clearly show a differentiation of geological environments by electrical resistivity, which allows for a more confident separation of lithological varieties and zones of cracking, as well as delineation of contact surfaces between different rock types. The variations in electrical resistivity observed in the studied profiles provide a basis for distinguishing water-saturated zones, mylonitised and clayey areas from more compact and less fragmented rock complexes.

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